

**King's Evangelical Divinity School and
University of Chester**

**A HERMENEUTICAL CRITIQUE OF THE
WATCH TOWER BIBLE AND TRACT SOCIETY'S
"FAITHFUL SLAVE" DOCTRINE OF MATTHEW 24:45**

**A Dissertation Presented in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for the
Bachelor of Theology**

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ABSTRACT

The Watch Tower Bible and Tract Society of Pennsylvania (hereafter “Watch Tower”) has consistently claimed the principle of *sola scriptura*. However, in point of fact, when it comes to exegesis, Jehovah’s Witnesses rely upon their leadership, namely, the “Governing Body”, for biblical interpretation. Hermeneutical authority rests in the concept that the Governing Body prophetically fulfils the office of “faithful slave” mentioned in Matthew 24:45. This slave is said to be responsible for interpreting and disseminating biblical “truths” to members. It is the aim of this research to locate Matthew 24:45 within Watch Tower hermeneutical theory in order to analyse whether or not this doctrine is credible. Research follows three main foci: a historical review tracing hermeneutical antecedents, followed by the literature review engaging current scholarship, and finally an exegesis of vv.45-51. Research findings conclude that the Watch Tower is guilty of extreme eisegesis, thereby invalidating its claim to be the “faithful slave” of Matthew 24:45. Final conclusions outline the eclectic nature of Watch Tower hermeneutics while identifying a knowledge gap, namely, how reader-response criticism both forged and maintains this doctrine. Finally, there is an urgency to educate the Church in relation to research findings with a view to reaching out into the Jehovah’s Witnesses community.

Key Words: interpretive authority, faithful slave, Governing Body, spiritual food

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It is my prayer that the information herein presented both stimulates further academic research and equips the saints with the necessary tools to dialogue successfully with Jehovah's Witnesses. Finally, my utmost thanks go to our heavenly Father, firstly, for his Son, and, secondly, for his continual empowering and illumination through the Holy Ghost. To YHWH be glory: one true God now and forever. Amen and amen.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CJB	Complete Jewish Bible
EOB	Eastern Orthodox Bible
JB	Jerusalem (Catholic) Bible
KJV	King James Version
MB	<i>The Message</i> Bible
MT	Majority Byzantine Text
NASB	New American Standard Bible
NWT	New World Translation
SBL	Society of Biblical Literature Greek New Testament
TR	Textus Receptus (1550)
WH	Westcott & Hort Greek New Testament
WTBTS	Watch Tower Bible and Tract Society of Pennsylvania

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

“Who really is the *faithful and discreet slave* whom his *master appointed* over his *domestics*, to give them their *food at the proper time*?” (Matthew 24:45 NWT, emphasis added). For over one hundred and thirty years the Watch Tower has consistently interpreted v.45 as being prophetically fulfilled through its religious movement:

The timely *spiritual food* [literature] we receive is proof that Jesus ... is keeping his promise to feed us. When giving the sign of his presence [1874/1914], Jesus said that he would use “*the faithful and discreet slave*” to give “*food at the proper time*” to his domestics. ... That faithful slave is the *channel* through which Jesus is feeding his true followers. ... Who, then, is the *faithful and discreet slave*? ... That slave has been closely identified with the *Governing Body* of Jehovah’s Witnesses. (WTBTS, 2013, pp. 20-22, emphasis added)

Herein is encapsulated the Watch Tower doctrine of the “faithful and discreet slave” (hereafter “faithful slave”), a hierarchal teaching system said to descend from Jehovah through Jesus to his earthly channel, namely, the Governing Body (Fig. 1). Comprising seven men (WTBTS, 2015c), this elite group is said to provide the “household of faith” its “spiritual food at the proper time”.

Former Governing Body member Raymond Franz (2007) astutely observed, “In their call for loyalty and submission, no other portion of Scripture is so frequently appealed to by the Governing Body of Jehovah’s Witnesses” as Matthew 24:45. “It is employed primarily to support the concept of a centralized administrative authority, exercising extensive control over all members” (p. 125). Moreover, the Governing Body is fully responsible for Watch Tower hermeneutical theory; so absolute is its interpretive control that members are counselled against independent study:

Heavy research is not necessary. The Watch Tower has done it for you. The most beneficial study you can do is read the *Watchtower* and *Awake* or a new book by the organization. (WTBTS, 1967b, p. 338)

Consequently, members rely completely on the Governing Body for all biblical interpretations. Should a member have a Bible question, a plethora of Watch Tower articles are on hand to answer. Of course,

members are fully convinced of the accuracy of this information. Nevertheless, the question of legitimacy must be addressed, for if Matthew 24:45 has been exegeted incorrectly, then the centralized authority of the Governing Body is thrown into question.

1.2 Focus and value of research

Much has been written on the belief system of Jehovah's Witnesses. Despite this, there remains a paucity of academic literature analysing Watch Tower hermeneutics. It is the focus of this research to address, in part, this deficiency primarily through analysis and exegesis of Matthew 24:45. Once conclusions are complete, recommendations will be formulated for educational outreach.

The value of this research transcends academia, for if the Watch Tower interpretation of Matthew 24:45 is false, then the Governing Body can no longer justify its magisterial position. The ramifications are incalculable, for without the Governing Body, hypothetically, the organization ceases to exist.

1.3 Overall objective of research

Overall research is aimed at advancing the notion that the Watch Tower has incorrectly interpreted Matthew 24:45, thereby invalidating its claims to be the prophetic fulfilment of the "faithful slave".

However, to realize this overall aim, four secondary objectives must be achieved:

1. trace historical antecedents (chapter 1);
2. define the "faithful slave" doctrine (chapter 1);
3. identify hermeneutical theory and praxis (chapter 2); and
4. exegete Matthew 24:45 (chapter 3).

Research vehicles include: primary Watch Tower sources, in-depth review of relevant literature, historical research, and employment of the historical-grammatical method of exegesis. Research methodology follows a cause and effect historical format, firstly identifying antecedents to Russellian thought, then tracing the historical development of the "faithful slave" doctrine terminating in comparative exegesis of Matthew 24:45.

Chapter 2

HISTORICAL ANTECEDENTS

2.1 Introduction

As with many unique doctrines, the Watch Tower interpretation of Matthew 24:45 was not birthed in a void. Rather the “faithful slave” emerges out of antecedent theologies adopted by C. T. Russell from “the regular doctrines of a few Adventist preachers” (Johnson, 2015, p. 151). Thus research begins with a necessary review of Adventism (Fig. 4).

2.2 Adventism and historicist premillennialism

By the late eighteenth century, historicist premillennialism as advanced by Adventists was in disarray (Crompton, 1996, p. 30). Confusion was due in part to prophetic speculation. Historicists believed the prophetic material (Daniel 8:14; 12:7, 11-12; Revelation 11:3-6) unfolded throughout history until the return of Christ. To unlock the hidden “plan of the ages”, Adventists employed the “day-for-a-year” principle. This provided the exegete with a method whereby each prophetic day equalled one year. Thus by matching historic events with key prophetic texts, complex chronologies were created and Advent dates set.

The founder of Adventism, William Miller (1782-1849), settled upon the Second Advent date of 1844 (Knight, 2010). However, with failure came the need for explanations. These came in the form of spiritualization. Supposedly literal events were deemed to have occurred in “heavenly places” unseen to human eyes. Thus the timing of the event was said to be correct but the expectation was said to be in error. Herein spiritualization conveniently provided a self-correcting methodology, one which evolved out of necessity; non-appearance had to be dealt with, otherwise exegesis was demonstrably false. ‘It is against this [historical and hermeneutical] background that Russell must be understood’ (Crompton, 1996, p. 30).

2.3 Russellian hermeneutics

Charles Taze Russell was born in Allegheny, Pittsburgh, on February 16, 1852 (Gruss, 1970, p. 38). Having become disillusioned with traditional Church doctrine, Russell, aged only seventeen, joined a

local Adventist group led by Jonas Wendell. At this juncture, Russell began to exegete Scripture ‘through the lens of Wendell’s brand of Adventism’ (Zydek, 2010, p. 31). Wendell espoused the hermeneutical theory of Adventist Nelson H. Barbour. Already by 1873, Barbour had proposed 1874 as Christ’s Second Advent and 1914 as the end of the age (Schulz, 2009). For in-depth analysis of 1914, see Jonsson (2004).

Russell subsequently adopted both 1874 and 1914 into his own chronological system (Fig. 2). However, with Christ’s first non-appearance (1874), serious doubts arose over the reliability of the historicist method—Barbour eventually abandoned the whole system (Zydek, 2010, pp. 52-60). Despite this, Adventist B. W. Keith proposed that Jesus had indeed returned in 1874, but invisibly. His argumentation focused upon the Greek word, *parousia* (Matthew 24:3). By drawing upon the work of Adventist and autodidact Bible scholar, Benjamin Wilson, Keith believed Wilson’s *Emphatic Diaglott* (1864) offered a “logical” answer. Herein, Wilson translated *parousia* as “presence”, indicating a spiritual presence in the world unseen to the naked eye. Many, including Russell, accepted Keith’s reasoning claiming, “It will be the eye of understanding, not the eye of flesh” that recognizes Christ’s return in 1874 (Zydek, 2010, p. 45). Analogous with 1844, the spiritualizing of 1874 acted as a self-correcting method against prophetic failure.

Convinced that an end-time harvest was underway, Russell gave expression to his views through his pseudo-Adventist journal, *Zion’s Watch Tower and Herald of Christ’s Presence*, launched in July 1879. The first-ever edition made its objectives very clear: “to be the lookout from whence matters of interest ... may be announced to the ‘little flock’ and as the ‘herald of Christ’s presence’ to give the ‘meat in due season’ to the ‘household of Faith’” (Russell, 1879, pp. 1-6). Note the embryonic beginnings of the “faithful slave” doctrine.

2.4 Towards a definition of the “faithful slave” doctrine

From this all too brief survey of Adventism and Russellian thought, research now turns to Matthew 24:45 and the historical development of the “faithful slave” doctrine from 1881 to 2013. Research draws upon primary Watch Tower sources.

2.4.1 Russell

The *Watch Tower* magazine of 1881 carried an article, “In the vineyard” (Russell, 1881, pp. 4-6), in which Russell dealt with Matthew 24:45. He concluded that the “faithful servant” was the composite “body of Christ” that was “individually and collectively, giving the meat [literature] in due season to the household of faith” (p. 5).

Later, in 1895, the *Watch Tower* carried an article, “Watchfulness” (Russell, 1895, pp. 88-91). Here Russell identifies himself and his followers as “Watchers”—that is, those whom had “declared and recognized” Christ’s invisible return in 1874. Russell further advanced the idea that the “Watchers” paralleled the “faithful slave” of Matthew 24:45, forming a composite slave class. However, this interpretation underwent metamorphosis in 1896:

The term “that servant” [is used] as though ... we applied it to all true servants of God. ... The objection urged is that the Lord’s words clearly mention and distinguish between his “household” (his faithful people in general), the “fellow-servants” (plural) and “that servant” specially indicated as the Lord’s agent in dispensing present truth as food to his “fellow-servants” and the “household”. It is further suggested that *whoever occupies the position of “that servant” occupies a place of ... special privilege. ... the food will be dispersed through a steward* to “fellow-servants” and the “household” in general. (Russell, 1896, pp.47-48, emphasis added)

Here is clear evidence of interpretive evolution. The phrase “that servant” once interpreted corporately is now assigned a singular meaning. Firstly, “that servant” is said to occupy a “place of special privilege”, his role being to disperse spiritual truths to his fellow servants. The inference is clear: Russell is “that servant” and those closest to him are “fellow servants”. Further modification occurred in the article, “The faithful and wise steward”:

The implication seems to be that *when the right time should come for understanding the parable*, it would be clearly set forth: that at the time of the parable’s fulfilment the Lord would *appoint a servant* in the household to bring these matters to the attention of all. ... [The Lord would] use *one member* of his church as *the channel* or instrument through which he would send the appropriate messages. (Russell, 1904, pp. 123-127, emphasis added)

Herein a new term for Russell is coined; he is said to be “the *channel* or instrument through which [God sends] appropriate messages.” Not coincidentally, Russell and his wife, Maria, were the chief writers and editors of the *Watch Tower* journal. Together, they read Russell into v.45, thus creating the “faithful slave” doctrine *ex nihilo*. Following Russell’s death in 1916, for the next eleven years *Watch Tower* editors repeatedly affirmed that Russell was the “faithful servant” (WTBTS, 1917, p. 6049; WTBTS, 1922, p. 132).

During his tenure, Russell had predicted seven major events that would occur before or during 1914 (Russell, 1889, pp. 76-78). Of course, with the end of World War 1 in 1918, every last prediction failed. Similar to the Millerite situation of 1844, this millennial-orientated movement faced extinction. Bible Students had relied upon Russell to navigate Scripture and provide “food at the proper time”. With Russell gone, and his prophecies unfulfilled, unquestionably the “faithful slave” doctrine had to be revised.

2.4.2 Rutherford

Joseph Franklin Rutherford had joined the Bible Student movement in 1894 (Zydek, 2010, p. 144). He became president of the Watch Tower Society in 1917. Rutherford inherited a movement in disarray and schism (Fig. 3). Clearly, the year 1914 had not ushered in the millennium; correspondingly, journal subscriptions dropped from 45,000 (pre-war) to less than 3,000 (post-war) (Crompton, 1996, pp. 95-96). One surmises that Rutherford discerned early on that for the movement to survive, major theological changes were necessary. However, to handle these difficulties, Rutherford had first to overturn the notion that Russell had been the “faithful slave”. The challenge started in 1926, when Rutherford began to contradict ‘much of what had been claimed and taught as truth, even by Rutherford, for over thirty years’ (Gruss, 2007, p. 58). The result was a return to the 1881 understanding of “faithful slave”, namely, “when the Lord comes to his temple he finds a faithful and wise *class*” (WTBTS, 1927, p. 55).

Rutherford’s regressive interpretation highlights the inconsistent nature of Watch Tower hermeneutical praxis. However, this was nothing new. Russell himself had subscribed to what he called “progressive theology; a concept, which anticipates that a developing body of information, and

those who accept it as truth, must be prepared to accept changes as new light is shed on any given subject” (Zydek, 2010, p. 81). Consequently, the old light of 1881 became the new light of 1926.

In a landmark article entitled, “Birth of a nation” (Rutherford, 1925; Wright, 2014), Rutherford employed Russellian logic. Just as, through spiritualization, Russell taught Christ had returned invisibly in 1874, now Rutherford proposed 1914 as the birth of God’s kingdom. The transference of Christ’s invisible presence from 1874 to 1914 occurred gradually, the two dates oftentimes appearing in contradiction (Jonsson, 2004, p. 58). However, from 1930 onwards, 1914 took on greater prominence. “The second coming of Christ dates from the fall of the year 1914” (Rutherford, 1932, p. 48). Following the death of Rutherford in 1942, the date 1874 was finally erased, and 1914 became the official date of Christ’s Second Advent or invisible presence (WTBTS, 1973a, p. 209). By the 1940s, Russell’s chronological system had been all but abandoned (Fig. 5). New prophetic dates were proposed; Jesus had inspected Christendom in 1918, rejecting it along with all false religion, commerce, and politics in favour of the Watch Tower Society, whom he appointed “faithful slave” in 1919 (WTBTS, 1988, p. 32).

Note how the Watch Tower interpreters arbitrarily imbue their own history and unique doctrines back onto prophetic material. Of particular interest for this research is 1919, for it is in this year that post-Russellian editors claimed Matthew 24:45 was fulfilled, “represented [today] by the Governing Body of Jehovah’s Witnesses” (WTBTS, 2013, p. 22).

2.5 Conclusion

Russell was the product of his *Sitz im Leben*. He began with Adventism, and ended with Adventism, albeit a refined version. With his death and prophetic failures, organizational necessity forced Rutherford to progressively refine the “faithful slave” (Fig. 6) doctrine, without which the movement would invariably have vanished. Despite inconsistent interpretations, the outcome is the same. To be the “faithful slave” is to procure for oneself absolute administrative, theological, and hermeneutical authority over membership.

In summary, several exegetical presuppositions prevail. Firstly, Matthew 24:45 is approached as a prophetic parable. Secondly, the date of fulfilment, believed originally to be 1874, is now set at 1914, with the final appointment of the “faithful slave” said to be in 1919. Thirdly, the Watch Tower

claims its movement fulfils this parable. Exegetically speaking, these three presuppositions dictate biblical interpretation. The result is a narrowing of interpretative options to the point that only the Watch Tower version of events fits the parable, thus creating a self-fulfilling prophecy.

Chapter 3

LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 Introduction

The progressive nature of Watch Tower interpretation throws into question the Governing Body's hermeneutical credibility, for how can a discarded "truth" return to be a "new truth", and vice versa? To answer, the literature review engages scholarship with a view to locating and defining Watch Tower hermeneutics. Conclusions will in turn elucidate Matthew 24:45 and the "faithful slave" doctrine.

Out of academic propriety, a letter pertaining to Watch Tower hermeneutics (see Appendix) was forwarded to Watch Tower headquarters in Brooklyn, New York, thus affording the opportunity to dialogue. No acknowledgement or response has been received.

3.2 Towards a definition of Watch Tower hermeneutical theory and praxis

According to Penton (2002, p. 177), Russellian hermeneutics consist of a "hodge-podge of ideas borrowed from the enlightenment (logic and human reason), early Christianity, Judaism, medieval Catholicism and Anglo-American Protestantism"—that is, Adventism. Combining these ideas, Russell focused his interpretive prowess on prophecy. The result was a complex chronological system maintained by allegory, typology, and rationalism (Van Baalen, 1962, p. 267).

Making sense of modern Watch Tower hermeneutics is extremely difficult because Jehovah's Witnesses have no systematic theology or interpretive methodology (Penton, 2002, p. 159). Nevertheless, certain concepts drive both doctrine and interpretation.

Primary is the "faithful slave" doctrine, followed closely by progressive theology or "New Light" theory. Drawing upon Proverbs 4:18, which speaks of "the path of the righteous ... getting brighter ... until the day is firmly established", the Watch Tower applies this pericope to itself, claiming that Jehovah enlightens the Governing Body *gradually*. This concept of "gradual light" encourages members to stay abreast with current thinking or else get left in the dark. It is characteristic of closed communities that members look to the organization for the latest revelations (Houlden, 2002,

p.77; Beckford, 1975). Older Watch Tower literature, especially that which contradicts current theology, is automatically rejected as “old light”.

Gilmour (2006, p. 8) identifies the “apparent uniformity in theology (tracts, website, door-to-door ministry, etc.)” as owing “something to the organization’s massive publishing initiative that ensures all members are reading the same texts” (cf. WTBTs, 2016b). Furthermore, Gilmour (2006, p. 3) argues, “Watch Tower publications blur the traditional boundaries that distinguish sacred literature from interpretation, so much so [that Watch Tower literature] functions, in effect, as Scripture for this particular reading community”. Of course, Jehovah’s Witnesses would deny this observation, claiming interpretation is by *sola scriptura*. However, in reality, the biblical canon alone is not sufficient. Instead, the organization and its literature operate as the hermeneutical mechanism by which members comprehend the sacred text:

Jehovah’s visible organization [“faithful slave”] under Christ is a channel for bringing divine interpretation of his word to his devoted people. (WTBTs, 1938, p. 169) ... The Bible cannot properly be understood without Jehovah’s visible organization. (WTBTs, 1967c, p. 587) ...

Only this organization functions for Jehovah’s purpose. To it alone God’s Sacred Word, the Bible, is not a sealed book. (WTBTs, 1973b, p. 402)

Similar to the Catholic magisterium (Penton, 2002, p. 160) or the “Sanhedrin of Bible times”, the Governing Body of Jehovah’s Witnesses acts as both a “judicial court” and a “legislative body” (Franz, 2004, p. 56). Anyone disagreeing with this “faithful slave” is deemed apostate and duly sanctioned. “False apostles ... claim that God does not have an organization, and deny that Jesus received Kingdom power in 1914. ... these ridiculers ... these deceivers [the elders] disfellowship them from their congregations”. (WTBTs, 1988, p. 33)

Jehovah’s Witnesses are thus trapped in what Bowman (1991, p. 91) calls a “hermeneutical circle”, which consists of two levels. The first “is primary doctrine ... a system of interlocking beliefs ... that both rely on each other and reinforce each other and remain consistent” (i.e., annihilationism, conditionalism, Arianism, invisible presence, etc.). The “second level consists of secondary doctrines” (blood transfusions, birthdays, Christmas, etc.) that within the *Sitz im Leben* of members are important but can nevertheless be changed without “logical impact on the primary system”. (Bowman, 1991, p. 93) (Fig. 7)

Consequently, members “interpret Scripture in light of the pronouncements passed down” by the “faithful slave”, to the point that each Witness “is brainwashed so that he [or she] develops a way of thinking which is utterly incapable of understanding the Bible apart from Watchtower explanations” (Gruss, 1970, p. 216). Rules of interpretation are therefore irrelevant; members simply read, absorb, and accept:

The Watchtower [magazine] assists in understanding the Bible, its study is ... imperative. ... If we have love for Jehovah and the organization of his people we shall not be suspicious, but shall, as the Bible says, “believe all things,” all the things that *The Watchtower* brings out. (WTBTS, 1967a, p. 156)

Hoekema (1969, pp. 249-255) identifies five oddities of Watch Tower methodology:

1. absurd literalism;
2. absurd typology;
3. “knight-jump exegesis”—jumping around the Bible with utter disregard for context to secure a preconceived idea;
4. “rear-view method”—some historical event in the past is located, then particular Scripture texts are searched for and made to apply; the event is then termed fulfilled prophecy; and
5. rationalism—rejecting whatever in Scripture appears contrary to reason (i.e., the Trinity, hell, the soul), resulting in a system of denials.

Despite these observations, a knowledge gap exists. Few scholars recognize that as a reading community, the “faithful slave” creates new meaning according to organizational needs. For example, Russell interpreted Matthew 24:45 in light of the year 1874. Likewise, Rutherford interpreted Jesus’s parable in light of 1919. Both men operated within the metanarrative of their religion, each allowing their personal *Sitz im Leben*, life experiences, and theological bias a role in creating new meaning.

Such methodology may well be a form of reader-response criticism. This is not to be confused with total autonomy of the text, wherein meaning exists only in the mind of the reader, for the Watch Tower is always keen to assert textual authority. However, this position is not consistent, mainly because the Watch Tower follows no interpretive rules. Osborne (2006, p. 478) notes that in reader-response criticism, the “reading strategy develops within [the] interpretive community uniting the

text” with historical events, thus producing new meaning. In other words, the “faithful slave”—who here represents the reading community—arbitrarily takes Matthew 24:45 and links it with 1874 and 1919 to create new meaning. Consequently, the question of authorial intent is ignored; rather, outside presuppositions—“expectations, projections, conclusions, judgments, and assumptions”—control the reading process (Fish, 1981, p. 2). Therefore, the goal is not to “discover what the text is saying”, but rather to actualize preconceived ideas via the reading community. Texts are thus seen as open and progressive. Ironically, if the Watch Tower did limit meaning to the text itself, there would be no need for the “faithful slave” to explain meaning or clarify unfolding insights (Gilmour, 2006, p. 10).

3.3 Conclusion

Biblical interpretation for Jehovah’s Witnesses is not an individual matter. Rather, interpretation is viewed as the sole prerogative of the Governing Body. Matthew 24:45 is enlisted as a proof text to support the notion that God has an earthly channel through which he “feeds” members.

In summary, Watch Tower hermeneutical theory and praxis follow no defined rules but rather are birthed out of an eclectic mixture of theories and theologies all driven by organizational needs or expectations (reader-response). The “faithful slave” and “New Light” doctrines exemplify how allegory, hyper-typology, spiritualization, proof texting, and even Gnosticism inform interpretation (Zydek, 2010, p. 265).

Chapter 4

EXEGESIS OF MATTHEW 24:45-51

4.1 Introduction

Post-modernists would argue that Watch Tower interpretations are relative and therefore are as valid as any other, whereas Jehovah's Witnesses would likely appeal to 1914 and 1919 as corroborative evidence that the "faithful slave" doctrine is true. However, neither relativism nor chronological speculations are adequate reasons to accept the Watch Tower interpretation of Matthew 24:45. This is because argumentation stems from subjective methodologies that actually violate original meaning. To avoid such error, rules of interpretation are hereby deemed necessary prerequisites to objective analysis and final conclusions. Following this premise, research now turns to exegesis of Matthew 24:45.

4.2 Hermeneutical methodology

The writer here assumes the authenticity, authority, and unity of the biblical text in its canonical context (Osborne, 2006, pp. 37-56). As such, the hermeneutical task is to interpret original meaning: What did the author wish to convey to his audience? With this presupposition, interpretive rules will follow the historical-grammatical method. This methodology sets the parameters of acceptable and unacceptable contextualization (exegesis). Principles employed include:

- identifying the genre of literature;
- employing a literal hermeneutic—unless otherwise contextually indicated;
- attending to grammar;
- apprehending the historical circumstances;
- identifying authorial intent and audience;
- attending to textual context; and
- relating the textual parts to 1. the individual book and 2. the whole Bible, thus arriving at diachronic meaning (how the parts fit the overall biblical narrative).

4.2.1 Passage selected—reasons for choosing

The Watch Tower claims Matthew 24:45 found fulfilment in 1919. At that time, Christ is said to have inspected all of Christendom and found only the Watch Tower faithful to his cause, subsequently appointing this organization as his “faithful slave” (WTBTS, 2013). Therefore, v.45 presents a crucial theological proof text for the Watch Tower movement. Upon this text rests the interpretive authority of the Governing Body.

4.2.2 Important words

“Who really is the *faithful and discreet slave* whom his *master appointed* over his *domestics*, to give them their *food at the proper time*?” (NWT, emphasis added). The important words are interpreted thus:

1. “faithful and discreet slave”—a composite group of “anointed” Witnesses called the “Governing Body”;
2. “master”—Jesus Christ;
3. “food”—Watch Tower literature; and
4. “domestics”—Jehovah’s Witnesses who read the literature.

Together, these points could be paraphrased: “The Governing Body is the faithful and discreet slave whom Jesus Christ has appointed to publish and distribute Watch Tower literature as spiritual food to all its members.” However, if through sound exegetical practice Watch Tower interpretations are proved invalid, then the organization’s whole doctrinal structure and legitimacy will be called into question (Gruss, 1970, p. 215).

4.2.3 Setting of pericope

Verse forty-five forms part of the “faithful servant” parable (vv.45-51). In turn, the parable is set amidst the eschatological expectation of Matthew 24, namely, the *parousia* or Second Advent of Christ (v.3). “Moreover Christ utters this parabolic discourse by way of answering Peter’s question *Lord, are you telling this parable for us or for all?*” (Spence-Jones, 1909, pp. 443–444, referencing Luke 12:41), placing the discourse firmly between master and disciples.

Taken in isolation, the parable portrays an absentee landowner who leaves his estate in the management of a steward who in turn was responsible for other servants. Such real life situations were commonplace throughout the ancient Near East, as were period stories of similar type. Hence directly or indirectly, the original audience would have easily comprehended the watchful slave parable, which itself becomes the vehicle through which to comprehend Jesus's spiritual lesson (Keener, 2014, p. 110).

4.2.4 Genre of pericope

The genre of literature is parabolic (v.32); as such, a wholly literal interpretation is unjustified. Nevertheless, Jesus does employ apocalyptic language concerning moral destinies, adding an element of literalism. Most importantly for this research, v.45 is not prophetic in the sense of finding fulfilment outside of the final eschaton. Instead, the parable acts "to cast alongside, implying comparison or juxtaposition" (Bailey & Vander Broek, 1991, p. 106). Likewise, parables aim to "teach a spiritual truth" (Mickelsen, 1981, p. 215). Hence the author records Jesus's words for two main reasons: to make a comparison between master and disciple, and to convey a spiritual truth, namely, the consequences of being faithful or unfaithful. Final outcomes (reward and punishment) find fulfilment at the *parousia*.

4.2.5 Author and date of composition

Various ancient traditions affirm the apostle Matthew as author (Guthrie, 1990, pp. 43-48). The date of writing is disputed; however, accepting Christ's predictive power suggests an early composition during AD 50-64 (Guthrie, 1990, pp. 54-55).

4.2.6 Audience and purpose

Matthew contains many Old Testament references; citations and allusions suggest that this Gospel had an apologetic purpose for a Jewish audience (Keener, 1993, p. 45; Guthrie, 1990, pp. 32-37; France, 1985, pp. 17-20). Focusing on chapter 24, the author here records Jesus's great eschatological discourse. In this dialogue, Christ speaks to his attentive disciples about the signs of his return and the consummation of the age. Concerning Matthew 24:45-51, the immediate contextual audience is

Jesus's disciples, whereas for Matthew his audience is most likely Jews. The objective of the parable is to challenge the hearers/readers on their "faithfulness" to Christ.

4.3 The text

Analysis now turns to the pericope.

4.3.1 Translation comparison

Literal translations:

Who then is the faithful and sensible slave whom his master put in charge of his household to give them their food at the proper time? (NASB)

Who then is a faithful and wise servant, whom his lord hath made ruler over his household, to give them meat in due season? (KJV)

Dynamic equivalence translations:

Who is the faithful and sensible servant whose master puts him in charge of the household staff, to give them their food at the proper time? (CJB)

Who here qualifies for the job of overseeing the kitchen? A person the Master can depend on to feed the workers on time each day. (MB)

Both literal and dynamic equivalence translations convey the following main points:

1. The master
 - asks a question: "Who is the faithful and sensible slave?"
2. The servants
 - must qualify for appointment over the household.
3. The household
 - requires regular meals at the correct time.
4. The qualification:
 - faithful obedience.
5. The appointment:
 - made by the master to those qualified.

The NWT renders this verse:

Who *really* is the faithful and discreet slave whom his master appointed over his domestics, to give them their food at the proper time? (emphasis added)

Overall, this is a literal translation apart from the additional word “really”. A comparison of other English translations failed to uncover a single occurrence of this word. Certainly there is no warrant for insertion from the original autograph. Why, then, this adverb? Research suggests that the word “really” has been introduced for theological reasons. The Watch Tower metanarrative teaches that while multiple organizations may claim to be “faithful and discreet”, only one *really* is, namely, the Governing Body—all others form a composite “evil slave”. Suffice to say, this adverb adds a subtle touch of Watch Tower theology acting to galvanize the Governing Body’s magisterial position.

4.3.2 Text summary

This short parable discusses two types of disciple, the faithful and the unfaithful (vv.45, 48). We are told the master of the household has gone away and those left in charge are expected to obediently serve the household. Faithfulness is rewarded with greater responsibility (v.46) whereas disobedience results in punishment (vv.48-51). Eschatological imminence pervades the parable raising the Second Advent question; who will work diligently while patiently awaiting the master’s return? (vv.46-49).

4.3.3 Grammar and syntax

A comparison of v.45 in Greek versions uncovered a variant, namely, *θεραπείας* in the Byzantine (MT, TR, EOB) and *οικετείας* in other Greek versions (WH, SBL). Juxtaposed, these read:

Τίς ἄρα ἐστὶν ὁ πιστὸς δοῦλος καὶ φρόνιμος, ὃν κατέστησεν ὁ κύριος αὐτοῦ ἐπὶ τῆς

θεραπείας αὐτοῦ, τοῦ δίδοναι αὐτοῖς τὴν τροφήν ἐν καιρῷ; (MT)

Τίς ἄρα ἐστὶν ὁ πιστὸς δοῦλος καὶ φρόνιμος ὃν κατέστησεν ὁ κύριος ἐπὶ τῆς

οικετείας αὐτοῦ τοῦ δοῦναι αὐτοῖς τὴν τροφήν ἐν καιρῷ; (WH)

The parallel version of Luke 12:42 seems to occasion the textual variant, because Luke uses *θεραπείας* and Matthew *οικετείας*. It is probable that copyists wanted to harmonize both versions by using the same word. Semantically, both words relate to the same type of servanthood. The only difference

might be that οἰκετείας refers to a household including servants, and θεραπειάς to specific servants in the household. However, both words are in the singular and thus relate to the corporate household.

Furthermore, concerning the timing of appointment, the Matthaean pericope (οἰκετεία: ὄν κατέστησεν ὁ κύριος ἐπὶ τῆς οἰκετείας αὐτοῦ) conveys the past tense (“has been appointed”), whereas the Lukan (θεραπεία: ὄν καταστήσει ὁ κύριος ἐπὶ τῆς θεραπειάς αὐτοῦ) conveys the future tense (“will be appointed”). Possibly the historical Jesus related a longer parable that included the master returning home to reward his servant. This would explain why Matthew uses the aorist form κατέστησεν (v.45). In this way, Matthew may have used only a small part of the original parable, clustering various eschatological sayings together. If Luke were written later, he may have employed καταστήσει in v.42 because it is more consistent with v.44. Whatever the reason, the basic sense to “set down” develops the concept “to set in or install into office” (Kittel, Friedrich, & Bromiley, 1985). Thus despite anomalies, the overall outcome is the same: the appointment by the master of the faithful slave over his household.

4.4 Exegesis

Analysis now turns to original meaning and application.

4.4.1 Original meaning

24:45: Jesus’s parabolic response to Peter’s question, “Lord, are you telling this parable for us or for all?” (Luke 12:41), begins with an interrogative exhortation: “**Who then is the faithful and sensible slave?**” Christ here employs comparison. Clearly, the master represents Jesus and the slaves represent his disciples. However, the challenge to Peter and the gathered disciples is by way of self-examination: Are they fit for the job? First, they must be πιστός—faithful, trustworthy, dependable, reliable. Next, they must be φρόνιμος—wise, prudent, understanding in a practical sense. Finally, they must be δοῦλος—subservient to, and controlled by, Christ (Louw & Nida, 1996). To be a true disciple, one served the needs of others. Jesus had regularly inculcated this mentality, counselling his disciples that “whoever would be great among you must be your servant, and whoever would be first among you must be your slave” (Matthew 20:26-27).

Evidence of faithfulness depends upon how the slave discharged his responsibilities while the master was absent. Oftentimes, a wealthy householder gave high-level slaves positions of stewardship, much like a manager (Keener, 2014, p. 110). Responsibilities would include rationing out food to other household slaves—“the idea is that some good and true slave is raised to the stewardship of his master’s household” (Spence-Jones, 1909, pp. 443-444). Against this cultural background, Jesus weaves the parable.

24:46: “Blessed is that servant whom his master will find so doing when he comes.” Here, Jesus virtually answers his own question. The faithful servant is the one whom upon the master’s return is found “blessed” for performing the duties assigned. The phrase “when he comes” subtly introduces the eschaton. Christ—the master—will be absent for an unspecified time period. Those faithful at his Advent are called μακάριος or “blessed”—“pertaining to being happy, with the implication of enjoying favorable circumstances” (Louw & Nida, 1996). This state of happiness is not due to the return of the master, but internally realized through willing obedience. Thus Christ, through comparison, presents to his disciples a lesson in perseverance; to be “blessed”, they must discharge their duties diligently while patiently awaiting their master’s return.

24:47: “Truly, I say to you, he will set him over all his possessions.” Herein is the reward for faithfulness: no longer is the steward superintendent of a small household; his master now “sets him over all his possessions”—“One who is faithful in a very little is also faithful in much, and one who is dishonest in a very little is also dishonest in much” (Luke 16:10). The details of this reward are not given and it is perhaps unwise to press the interpretation. Suffice to say, καταστήσει ἐπὶ in the dative denotes permanency of occupation (Spence-Jones, 1909, p. 444), and the eschatological location is not identified. Clearly, the parable is set on earth; however, at the end of the age, cosmic changes are foretold (Isaiah 65:17; 2 Peter 3:13; Matthew 24:35; Revelation 21:1). Hence, the purpose here is comparison, not literalism. The message for Jesus’s followers: Continue faithfully, and you will receive permanent occupancy and reward (1 Corinthians 2:9).

24:48: “But if that evil slave says in his heart, ‘My master is not coming for a long time’”. Christ here introduces the antithetical evil slave. The opposite of “faithful and discreet”, this slave says in his heart, “my master delays.” Convinced the master will not return anytime soon, the evil slave puts off his personal day of reckoning believing he has plenty of time to resolve his

misdemeanours. Eschatological imminence is replaced by apathy and indifference. The message for Jesus's disciples: Even if I should delay, continue in faithful service.

24:49: “and begins to beat his fellow slaves and eats and drinks with drunkards”. Once the evil slave has convinced himself of his master's delay, his conduct changes. He assumes to be the master. Self-aggrandizement is the order of the day. Household responsibilities and care of fellow slaves are abandoned. Self-indulgent, the evil slave chooses companions of loose conduct. The warning for Jesus's disciples: Do not fall prey to selfish desire, and do not abuse the authority I have bestowed upon you.

24:50: “the master of that slave will come on a day when he does not expect him and at an hour which he does not know”. Christ warns about the unknown timing of his return using eschatological language: “But concerning that day or that hour, no one knows, not even the angels in heaven, nor the Son, but only the Father” (Mark 13:32). Nevertheless, his return is certain. Concerning the evil slave—“The awful hour was utterly unknown; but this has not made him watchful; hence he becomes unfaithful” (Spence-Jones, 1909, p. 444). The message to Jesus's disciples is clear: I am coming back; therefore, “Be on guard, keep awake. For you do not know when the time will come—for you do not know when the master of the house will come, in the evening, or at midnight, or when the rooster crows, or in the morning—lest he come suddenly and find you asleep. And what I say to you I say to all: Stay awake” (Mark 13:33, 36-37).

24:51: “and will cut him in pieces and assign him a place with the hypocrites; in that place there will be weeping and gnashing of teeth.” Impending judgement and retribution awaits the evil slave (1 Peter 4:5; 1 Enoch 22:3-14). Historically, slaves were viewed as the master's property; as such, the master had the right to punish as he saw fit. Both drunkenness and a banquet at the expense of the master were punishable offences. Interestingly, in Jewish culture, disembodiment was “considered too cruel” a punishment (Keener, 2014, p. 110). Despite this, Jesus employs the graphic phrase “cut him in pieces” (cf. 1 Samuel 15:33; 2 Samuel 12:31; Daniel 3:29). The pericope moves through temporal punishment and death to a final destiny wherein he assigns the evil slave “a place with the hypocrites”—this is post-mortem retribution. The faithless, deceitful hypocrite who injured his fellow slaves is destined for a place where there will be “weeping and gnashing of teeth” (JB; cf. Judith 16:17. Of course, this is highly figurative parabolic language; nevertheless, the purpose remains

consistent, namely, “to create mental images to enable people to understand the future reality of perdition” (Morey, 1984, p. 30). Moreover, the parable is inextricably linked with the end of the age, when “Jesus’ parables translate the lofty ideas of a final judgment and retribution in life after death into an awesome reality” (Young, 1998, p. 277).

4.4.2 Application

Having exegeted Matthew 24:45-51, the question of application arises. To whom—if anyone—does the parable apply? The number of options is limited by the parable itself. Original authorial intent is to quicken Christ’s disciples into faithful service. The four parabolic elements—Christ, a faithful servant, a household, and an evil servant—are set against the futurist Second Advent, and eschatological judgement and punishment.

With this in mind it may be argued that the parable spans the whole Christian age. From Pentecost until now, believers share the same heritage as “faithful slaves” and as such are inextricably linked to the parable. Likewise, the household of faith is not limited to the past but naturally incorporates all true believers. The spiritual lesson, then, is eternal. To be faithful to Christ means to be faithful to his calling within the household of faith. That may entail any number of different callings and appointments. Ultimately, the parable is Christological, and imminence pervades the parable, an imminence that is both a here-and-now reality and yet future (Matthew 28:20; John 14:3). Consequently, no matter what the *Sitz im Leben* of the individual Christian, each believer is encouraged to live out his or her faith within the household of God as a “faithful steward”—but always with one expectant eye on the master’s return. Diachronically speaking, the parable fits into the overall *Heilsgeschichte* of God, culminating with the eschaton, namely, Christ’s visible return, judgement, and retribution (Revelation 1:7; 1 Peter 4:5; 2 Corinthians 13:5). One final fact can be drawn from the parable: there remain evil slave tares that will grow alongside the true Church until the Second Advent (Matthew 13:29-30).

4.5 Conclusion

With the exegetical research complete, a comparison between the above findings and Watch Tower interpretation are in order. Two comparative questions arise.

Firstly, does the parable provide any exegetical basis for believing that Jesus returned invisibly in 1874 or 1914, or that in 1919 Jesus appointed the Watch Tower as his “faithful slave”? The answer is axiomatic: there is absolutely no exegetical warrant for imposing these dates and concepts back onto the original pericope. That being true, it follows that the modern-day Governing Body of Jehovah’s Witnesses cannot be identified with the “faithful slave” of Jesus’s parable. And secondly, to read the aforesaid history of the Watch Tower back into the parable is to do extreme violence to original authorial intent. In the final analysis, the Watch Tower is here guilty of extreme eisegesis (Fig. 8).

Chapter 5

CONCLUSION

5.1 Introduction

The overall aim of this research was to investigate the hermeneutical theory and praxis of the Watch Tower in connection with Matthew 24:45. Research findings prove this pericope is critical to how and why Jehovah's Witnesses read the Bible the way they do. Sub-points and secondary objectives were detailed in 1.3.

5.2 Research objectives and summary findings

What follows is a review of objectives, a summary of research findings, and final conclusions.

5.2.1 Defining the “faithful slave” doctrine

Chapter 2 explored antecedent factors to Russellian thought. Russell's conviction that Christ had returned invisibly in 1874 effectively straightjacketed biblical interpretation. For example, when approaching Second Advent passages such as Matthew 24:45, Russell's starting point was not the text itself, but the presupposition that v.45 had been fulfilled in 1874. All Russell felt he had to do was match historical events with the prophetic material. Invariably, Russell connected his own movement with Jesus's “faithful slave” parable (Matthew 24:45-51), eventually procuring the title for himself.

As research has shown, after the death of Russell and his complete prophetic failure, Rutherford revised the “faithful slave” doctrine, identifying the 144,000 as the composite slave. Out of necessity, Christ's 1874 *parousia* was moved to 1914, and Russell's chronological system reconfigured. Following Rutherford's death, further changes took place until, in 2013, the Governing Body of Jehovah's Witnesses was identified as the “faithful slave” of Matthew 24:45.

Summary findings show that the “faithful slave” doctrine has evolved out of two presuppositions:

1. Jesus returned invisibly in 1874 and 1914; and
2. Jesus appointed the Watch Tower organization as his “faithful slave” in 1919.

Once legitimized, the “faithful slave”—under whatever mantle—naturally became the epicentre of interpretive “truth”: Why look elsewhere if Jesus had appointed this group? Psychologically speaking, this belief entraps all members in what Cameron (2004, p. 5) calls an “illusionary concept”. The Watch Tower admits as much: “If [you] have become thoroughly convinced that this is Jehovah’s organization and that he is guiding and directing his people [you] shall not be unsettled by anything that happens” (WTBTS, 1957, p. 284) In other words, once “you are captive of the concept”, no amount of doctrinal inconsistency will unsettle you (Cameron, 2004, p. 13). This illusion is both circular and self-fulfilling.

5.2.2 Identifying hermeneutical theory and praxis

Chapter 3 encompassed the literature review. A definition of Watch Tower hermeneutics was deemed impossible, for the Watch Tower follows no rules of interpretation. Rather, its methodology is ad hoc, being informed primarily by presuppositions identified in 5.2.1. At best, its methodology follows prior Watch Tower traditions. These include historical premillennial hermeneutics, chronological speculation, spiritualization, hyper-typology, and Gnosticism (Fig. 7).

Despite this eclectic nature, research uncovered peculiarities that are imperative to Watch Tower interpretation. The first is the “faithful slave” doctrine. Without this, the Governing Body (“Jehovah’s organization”) has no legitimate right over interpretation. Second is “New Light” theology that essentially sanctions doctrinal changes without redress. Missing from current literature is a third imperative, namely, a form of reader-response criticism whereby the reading community dictates meaning. Applying these methods, the Watch Tower organization writes itself back into prophetic history, changing dates and doctrines at will, depending on the needs of the organization.

In summary three methodologies drive and control Watch Tower hermeneutics:

1. the “faithful slave” doctrine;
2. progressive theology/“New Light”; and
3. community-driven reader-response interpretation.

Furthermore, as a millennial movement, the Watch Tower is exegetically hamstrung by the assumption that Christ returned in 1914 (WTBTS, 2016a, 2016c). Logically speaking, the world must end sooner rather than later. Yet, as time passes, and with no apocalypse forthcoming, non-occurrence

must be explained. The likely solution will be a reconfiguration of doctrine according to the needs of the reading community (“faithful slave”)—a reader-response interpretation. Time will tell (Fig. 7).

5.2.3 Exegetical conclusions

Chapter 4 incorporated comparative exegesis of Matthew 24:45 by way of the historical-grammatical method. Interpretive rules therein reduced bias, the overall objective being to uncover authorial intent.

Research findings identify five parabolic elements:

1. the faithful slave—individual believer who discharges his/her calling faithfully;
2. master—Christ
3. the household—corporate body of Christ (the Church);
4. evil servant—false tare or unfaithful believer; and
5. appointment—rewards and judgements at the eschaton.

Authorial intent can be narrowed to three main groups:

1. contextual—Jesus and his disciples;
2. authorial—Matthew and his original audience; and
3. futurist—Jesus and his Church.

As a parable, the purpose is comparative, not literal or prophetic. However, the language employed was identified as eschatologically charged and therefore carries the “faithful slave” motif to the end of the age.

Exegetical findings vindicate research aims, namely, that the Watch Tower has incorrectly interpreted Matthew 24:45, thereby invalidating its claims to be the prophetic fulfilment of the “faithful slave” (Fig. 8).

5.3 The human cost

“Authority is the greatest and most irreconcilable enemy to truth and argument the world has ever furnished—against authority there is no defence” (Strong, McClintock, & Smith, 1982, pp. 553-554). Authority, as an enemy of both truth and freedom (Franz, 2007, p. 16), is exemplified in the “faithful slave” doctrine, which dictates truth claims to members. The process is subtle: once a person is convinced that “God himself is speaking directly through this organization”, he or she becomes the

“captive of an illusion” (Cameron, 2004, p. 12). Within this illusion occurs a mystical syncretism between the earthly “organization” (the Governing Body/“faithful slave”) and the heavenly organization. The word “organization” essentially connects heavenly and earthly with the overarching rule of Jehovah God. Hence, to speak ill of the Governing Body/“faithful slave” (God’s earthly expression) is viewed as direct rebellion against Jehovah because the two are synonymous. Once enamoured with this illusion, members live for the organization, conveying an almost Nazi-like obedience, giving up all critical thinking ability for fear of blaspheming Jehovah.

Of course, millions of faithful Witnesses are content with this status quo. However, research findings clearly demonstrate that this doctrine is extra-biblical, wholly fictitious, and therefore should be categorically rejected. More akin to the “Wizard of Oz”, the “faithful slave” doctrine is simply a grand hoax. As such, Jehovah’s Witnesses need no longer look to a human-made organization for “food at the proper time”. No human intermediary is necessary; rather, God himself draws, illuminates, and saves (Matthew 11:28; John 6:44; 8:32, 36; 14:6, 26; Ephesians 2:8).

5.4 Recommendations

Over eight million Jehovah’s Witnesses evangelize door-to-door each week (WTBTS, 2015a, 2015b). In terms of missionary work, they are unrivalled. During this ministry time, members encounter many evangelical Christians; sadly, the vast majority literally “shut the door” to dialogue. Therefore, education of the Church is imperative if this closed community is to be reached with the true Gospel. How this is actualized is harder to envision. It is suggested that Christian seminaries offer student modules specifically tailored to educate about Jehovah’s Witnesses, the apologetic data received—God willing—precipitating down through the pulpit into the pew. This would at least be a start; yet truly much is needed and the workers are few (Luke 10:2).

5.5 Contribution to knowledge

In terms of knowledge gaps, research has identified a form of reader-response criticism operating at the community level (“faithful slave”) within Watch Tower hermeneutics. Findings underscore that the “faithful slave” doctrine was both forged from community needs and is maintained by community

needs. The correlation of evidence adds weight to this hypothesis. It is hoped research findings will inspire further academic inquiry.

Omnia in gloriam Dei.

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Figure 1

Figure 2

THE CHRONOLOGICAL SYSTEM OF CHARLES TAZE RUSSELL

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

REVISED CHRONOLOGY OF J. F. RUTHERFORD TO PRESENT DAY

Figure 6

**WATCH TOWER INTERPRETIVE CHRONOLOGY
IDENTITY OF THE “FAITHFUL SLAVE”—MATTHEW 24:45**

Figure 7

Figure 8

MATTHEW 24:45—COMPARATIVE EXEGESIS		
Historical-grammatical interpretation	method	Watch Tower eclectic interpretation
parabolic—eschatologically charged, spanning the whole Christian era	genre	parabolic—wholly prophetic and literally fulfilled in 1919
Christ	“master”	Christ
individual Christians	“faithful slave”	Governing Body
individual calling within the Church	appointment	Governing Body over membership
discharge of calling within Church	“food at proper time”	publication of Watch Tower literature
Individual Christians are each appointed by Christ to various callings. To be faithful and discreet is to honor that calling within the household of faith (the Church) while awaiting his Second Coming. CONCLUSION = EXEGESIS	interpretive paraphrase	The Governing Body is the “faithful and discreet slave” appointed by Jesus Christ in 1919 to publish and distribute Watch Tower literature as spiritual food to all its members. CONCLUSION = EISEGESIS

Appendix

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Date: 30/10/2015
Watchtower Bible & Tract Society
25 Columbia Heights
BROOKLYN NY 11201-2483
UNITED STATES

Dear Sir/Madam,

My name is Jason Wright and I am currently finishing my Bachelor of Theology degree at Kings Divinity College in England.

For my final dissertation I have chosen as my subject matter the "Hermeneutics' of the Watchtower Society". This dissertation will explore the origins and evolution of the Watchtower's interpretive methodology from its inception in the 1870's up to the present today.

As there is very little published material on this subject I am seeking direct information from the Watchtower society itself, hence my letter. If at all possible I would be most grateful for information pertaining to your hermeneutical methodology. Below is a short survey that I hope you will be able to answer.

- 1) What hermeneutical methodology did Charles Taze Russell espouse?
- 2) Where did Charles Taze Russell receive his exegetical training?
- 3) Has the hermeneutical methodology of the Watchtower Society changed significantly over the decades? If yes please provide dates when changes occurred.
- 4) Please describe the hermeneutical methodology of the modern day Watchtower Society.
- 5) Do all members of the Watchtower Society adhere to the same hermeneutical methodology?

I look forward to hearing from you in due course,

Kind Regards

Pastor Jason Wright